

A VARIETY OF TRAP CROPS, DISTRACTING FROM THE MAIN VEGETABLE CROPS

¹Khudoykulov Azamjon Mirzokulovich, ²Hakimov Albert Akhmetovich, ³Norova Malika Nurillayevna, ⁴Gazieva Dilnoza Komiljonovna

¹PhD, associate professor

²PhD, associate professor

³PhD student

⁴Doctoral student of the Research Institute of Plant Protection and Quarantine in Uzbekistan

^{1,2,3}Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10868348>

Abstract. *Trap crops are used to repel pests away from the main vegetables by luring harmful insects onto their own leaves and stems. Farmers may have to deal with pests on decoy crops - whether it is manual harvesting or disposal of infected plants — but at least the main vegetables will not be affected.*

Keywords: *trap crops, dill, vegetables, cabbage, chervil, plant protection, biological plant protection.*

Introduction. Trap crops are a more environmentally friendly method of vegetable growing when it comes to preventing the destruction of major crops by pests than chemicals. It is better to sow or spread the baits at least a couple of weeks before sowing the main crops that need to be preserved. It is better to keep the crops that need to be protected at a distance of at least 1000 m from the bait crops.

Dill. Sometimes reaching adulthood with feathery foliage and umbrellas of yellow flowers, dill attracts tomato hawk moth. These large, green and disgusting creeping insects infect tomatoes and other crops belonging to the Solanaceae family.

However, keep in mind that tomato hawkmoths also turn into quite impressive moths. Dill is also a host plant for swallowtail butterflies, whose caterpillars are more beautiful than hawk moth, with white, yellow and black circles. Meanwhile, you can use any dill that has survived after using them as bait.

Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *viridis*). The same green, but smaller, cabbage worms are loved by all members of the Brassicaceae family. You can take advantage of the unpretentiousness of the cabbage worm by detaching it from the main type of cabbage, having previously sown cabbage leaves.

Fig.1. *Cabbage white butterfly – a pest of cabbage*

A simpler variety of cabbage with less curly leaves so that it can be planted outdoors a month before the date of the last frost, ensuring that early cabbage becomes infected with worms.

Evening primrose (*Oenothera biennis*). Speaking of beetles, one local flowering “weed” can help get rid of beetles. Although most gardeners pull out seedlings of wild evening primrose, it is a good idea to leave some seedlings at the edges of the garden, since biennial plants can grow up to 5 feet in the right conditions.

Fig.2. Evening primrose (*Oenothera biennis*) – decoy culture from beetles

They not only produce beautiful yellow nocturnal flowers, but also distract beetles from other plants. All parts of evening primrose plants, including seeds, are edible and probably more nutritious than many vegetables in the beds from which they are usually harvested.

Nasturtium (*Tropaeolum majus*). Nasturtium is native to South America. The family of these charming plants has several dozen (exactly 80) species, but not all of them are favored by our native climate. Individual plant species differ in color and shape of flowers or leaves and, of course, in size. Another bright and biting flower is nasturtium, which can distract all kinds of aphids from your zucchini, cabbage and beans.

Fig.3. Nasturtium (*Tropaeolum majus*) – decoy crop from aphids

Since pesky aphids tend to accumulate on the tips of plants, you can just keep pinching nasturtiums to rid them of “plant aphids”.

French calendula (*Tagetes patula*). The homeland of calendula is Southern and Central Europe, as well as Asia. But despite this, the beautiful yellow-orange flower grows well in colder regions. He pleases us with his flowers, as if the sun were shining. I think many people love him for that alone. In addition, this flower is very easy to grow.

Different peoples have found their use of calendula. Brave alchemists even tried to get gold by mixing other substances with the juice of flowers. Of course, they didn't succeed. The ancient Greek healers turned out to be more intelligent. They realized that marigold flowers

have antiseptic properties, and therefore used them in the treatment of wounds and insect bites. A decoction of calendula was used for gargling (it is still used today).

Fig.4. Aphids are a pest of vegetable crops

Thrips prefer calendula, thereby to some extent abandoning tomatoes or other perennial vegetable plants.

Fig.5. French calendula (*Tagetes patula*) – decoy crop from thrips

It was used as a decoy crop and as a pest control based on its smell.

Conclusion. Based on the above, we can conclude that decoy crops are an environmentally friendly method of protecting cultivated plants, since environmental protection and the production of environmentally friendly agricultural products is currently the most urgent problem in the world.

REFERENCES

1. Shelton, A.M.; Badenes-Perez, F.R. (2005-12-06). "Concepts and applications of trap cropping in pest management". *Annual Review of Entomology*. 51 (1): 285–308. doi:10.1146/annurev.ento.51.110104.150959. ISSN 0066-4170. PMID 16332213.
2. Jump up to:a b c d e f Holden, Matthew H.; Ellner, Stephen P.; Lee, Doo-Hyung; Nyrop, Jan P.; Sanderson, John P. (2012-06-01). "Designing an effective trap cropping strategy: the effects of attraction, retention and plant spatial distribution". *Journal of Applied Ecology*. 49 (3): 715–722. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2664.2012.02137.x. ISSN 1365-2664.
3. Alfredo Flores (March 8, 2010). "Geraniums Could Help Control Devastating Japanese Beetle". United States Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service. Retrieved 2010-04-04.
4. Swezey, Sean L.; Nieto, Diego J.; Bryer, Janet A. (2007-12-01). "Control of western tarnished plant bug *Lygus hesperus* Knight (Hemiptera: Miridae) in California organic strawberries using alfalfa trap crops and tractor-mounted vacuums". *Environmental Entomology*. 36 (6): 1457–1465. ISSN 0046-225X.[verification needed]

5. Samuel Fromartz (2005). *Organic Inc.: Natural Foods and How They Grew*. Harcourt. ISBN 978-0-15-603242-1.
6. Jaime Pinero (March 16, 2017). "Trap cropping: A simple, effective, and affordable Integrated Pest Management strategy to control squash bugs and squash vine borers". University of Missouri, Integrated Pest Management.
7. Р озанова, М.А. Обзор литературы по родам *Vaccinium* L. (брусника, черника, голубика) и *Oxycoccus* (Tonrr.) Hill (клюква) // Тр. по практ. бот., ген. и селекции. - 1934. - Сер. 8. - № 2.- С. 110 - 115.
8. Химический анализ лекарственных растений: Учеб. пос. для фармац. вузов / Е.Я. Ладыгина [и др.] / Под ред. Гринкевич Н.И., Сафронович Л.Н. - М.: Высш. школа, 1983. - 176 с.
9. Andersen, O.M. Anthocyanins in fruits of *Vaccinium uliginosum* L. (bog whortleberry) / O.M. Andersen. - J. Food Sci. - 1987. - № 52. -P. 665-666.